

MONITORING IS AN ESSENTIAL STAGE OF CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. The article reveals several beneficial sides of monitoring while the students are engaged in doing an activity. It is devoted to finding solutions to some issues of monitoring, such as when to monitor, how to monitor, what to monitor and why it is important to monitor.

Key words. Monitoring, guided practice, activity analysis, group interaction, instruction

INTRODUCTION. One of the key elements of classroom management - monitoring is roughly defined as paying a close attention to the students' accuracy as well as fluency when they are speaking, or confirming to see if things are moving according to expectations and that the students are busy with the very task. Although effective monitoring is a skill that must be developed if students are to fully benefit from activities, especially those of the information gap and group interactive types, it often goes out as a general listening and looking exercise by the instructor, and sometimes it is not done at all.

WHY WE NEED MONITORING.Development in learning never goes at the equal level. With the help of monitoring, we, as a teacher, can have the chance to evaluate how the students are progressing, and while monitoring, the teacher may be able to see what is insufficient and what to add to the effective learning style, what to practice more. Monitoring includes a few purposes at the lesson, looking at the stage of the lesson, what sort of tasks the students are engaged in, and the classroom environment.

a. Entire Class Awareness. The progress of the class should constantly be observed by the teacher so that she/he can be aware if the tempo is too brisk or inadequate, and to whom one-on-one support can be beneficial. There is frequently a propensity to focus on teaching the lesson plan and the materials rather than the students themselves.

- b. Listening for mistakes in the target language, especially during activities for guided practice. As these are typically accuracy-based activities, correction is necessary.
- c. Listening to make sure that students are paying attention. It can be necessary to repeat instructions, demonstrate the activity, or provide prompts.
- d. Using the chance to micro-teach individuals or pairs who are obviously struggling with the target language.
- e. Evaluating each person and the class as a whole. Monitoring offers hints about the struggles and development of both individuals and groups. In this way, monitoring is a continual needs assessment. Every student deserves some kind of attention, even if it's just a few words of support.
- f. Learners might not be able to maintain output, especially in fluency activities. The teacher's job is to inject language and concepts as needed to keep the exercise going.
- g. Measuring growth in fluency. This requires remote monitoring, and the teacher's job is frequently to make mental notes on frequent mistakes to be addressed in a delayed correction slot as well as to mentally note the usage of target language in a more relaxed context.
- h. Assignment Evaluation. Whereas some activities are being tried out for the first time, others work better with one class.. The ability to monitor gives the teacher the chance to evaluate an activity's effectiveness and gather student input.
- i. Organization. Monitoring makes it easier to make decisions on what to do next, whether to change the original lesson plan, how to plan upcoming lessons, and how to give students performance comments.
- j. Control Maintenance. If some students complete a work before others, large groups may become restless and bored. The teacher should have a few brief back-up exercises prepared for these students, or she/he might assign the faster students to assist slower groups.

FINDING THE EXACT TIME TO MONITOR

When the teacher is concerned with the overall assessment of learners' performance in regard to general progress or actual English and skill development, monitoring takes place constantly, but is particularly concentrated during speaking activities. During written practice tasks, where the goal is to point out faults and promote self-correction, individual learners are observed. Less directed groupwork activities are examined for productivity and fluency, whereas guided practice exercises, particularly those using the pairwork structure, are monitored for accuracy. A number of the following objectives may be the focus of general or multipurpose monitoring.

THE WAYS OF MONITORING

It's possible that monitoring will develop into a positive habit. While some teachers believe they should be involved at all times and that monitoring is the best course of action, less experienced teachers could feel that they must closely monitor and retain control of activities. In either scenario, there is a risk of over-monitoring, disruption, and a tense learning atmosphere during less directed practice sessions rather than a relaxed, student-centered one.

Close observation must be conducted with tact and requires a certain level of cultural and personal understanding. Some students dislike having the teacher hunched over in front of them, while others object to the teacher's intimate physical proximity. It is annoying and occasionally obtrusive to monitor from in front of the students, breaking up the action and turning attention to the teacher. Students then anticipate feedback from the teacher in the form of comments or corrections. Effective monitoring is done discreetly, and it is frequently done from behind the students. Here are a few advices:

- Detach chairs from walls.
- Ensure that the classroom has a clear path out of it.
- Seating should be arranged so that the teacher can see every student from any location.
- Randomly observe groups or couples.

- Spend a limited amount of time with each learner, whether they are an individual, a pair, or a group.
- Sit in pairs or groups as opposed to standing or crouching.
- The best way to move from group to group is in a chair with wheels.

Anywhere in the classroom can be used for remote monitoring, giving the opportunity to listen in on various talks. The teacher might need to walk around the room with larger classes. It's vital to avoid sitting next to one group the entire exercise, as this could imply that the teacher is just paying attention to them. The optimal location is frequently behind the students, out of their line of sight, where they may concentrate on the activity and one another rather than the teacher.

During more informal practice sessions, learners might want to raise questions. The teacher's answer will depend on the activity, but teaching the students to write down any questions they may have at the end of the activity is a good exercise in learner development. It is possible to watch oneself and others. Training in self-correction is a component of self-monitoring. All students may participate in peer monitoring, but a helpful strategy is to have them work in groups of three rather than pairs, with each student taking turns observing the other two's performance.

CONCLUSION

All teaching and learning scenarios can benefit from the aforementioned monitoring strategies, but in some cases, monitoring also serves as a means of enforcing discipline. In classrooms with less motivated or younger students, as well as frequently in monolingual and mixed-ability classes, there may be a temptation for the learners to give up, delegate the duty to pupils who are more capable, or just revert to speaking in their native tongue. Sometimes just having the teacher present in a supervisory capacity is sufficient, but diligent observation ensures the best performance from the students and offers the most insightful feedback for the teacher.

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